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**THE CONCEPT OF INTERACTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN
THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN
TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRIES**

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the core notion of interactive learning second language. The concept offers three different perspectives on this idea, including its role as a foundational principle in contemporary language teaching theory, as instructional methods, and as an approach to organizing foreign language instruction in vocational higher education institutions. The article focuses on the third definition of interactivity as a significant technique to compensate for student’s lack of expertise and professional experience when learning a foreign language for tourism and hospitality industries. Proficiency in numerous foreign languages is a prerequisite for effective communication in the tourism business, as well as mutual understanding among students participating in exchange programs with various universities, particularly in foreign countries. Tourism and mobility are important in this regard, as are intercultural interactions, which help to build intercultural conversation. Raising

awareness of the value of foreign language ability and encouraging the development of intercultural competency in the tourism and hospitality industries is critical.

KEYWORDS: *multilingualism, tourism, gadget, foreign language, online training, intercultural communication, gadgets, foreigners.*

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of foreign languages is essential, and multilingualism is considered as a long-term investment. With the European Union's continuing expansion, European language police are shifting toward teaching at least two foreign languages from a very early age and describing foreign language knowledge as a basic skill. Foreign language expertise clearly plays an important part in the development of tourism, which serves numerous functions and is considered as an economic, social, and cultural activity. As a result, it is undeniably one of the most essential activities of modern, current society around the world, particularly in Europe.

The creation of concepts about interactive technologies in education was heavily influenced by a number of previously well-known educational strategies and tactics. The idea that the learner should be an active participant in the learning process was at the heart of the cognitive approach to learning a foreign language, which employs primarily active teaching methods. According to the communicative-activity approach, the student should focus on learning as an active participant, autonomously setting and completing specific educational activities. The consistent with Reginald concept of "learning by action", which involves analyzing trainees' professional actions to identify and fill gaps in their own competence through interactive techniques. A new competence-based approach has demonstrated that students must develop certain sets of practical abilities, including professional ones, in order to operate productively in the business environment.

MAIN PART

In a broader sense, interactive learning allows a student to influence the content of his or her training, select appropriate courses and modules from the proposed set of disciplines, design and modify their own training package for the discipline, and express satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the educational product or process. For the teacher, interaction in learning also implies sensitive reflection on trainee's reactions, rather than simply adhering to their learning goals. In this regard, interaction can be viewed as one of the most modern and relevant ideas for teaching foreign languages. The key to comprehending interactivity is "the availability of operational feedback".

METHODS

Interactivity, like the degree of reaction, is explored as a communication process in which each message is related with prior communications and the relation of these messages to the messages before them. The learner's direct awareness of the success or failure of their speech behavior is a sign of the interactive nature of learning a foreign language. The idea of the interaction manifests itself in the most different ways in the corresponding methodical producers and interactive teaching methods used in foreign language training. We only present a subset of various types of classroom work. Interactive linguistic games are built on communication partnerships and participant reaction times. These include games for speech etiquette formulae, circle dialogues throughout the chain in which each participant serves as both a reacting and starting link, sentence generator, business card contest, and commercial and contest. All games contests are accompanied by explicit assessment criteria that allow for a thorough debate and evaluation of the best outcomes. Computer interactive technologies are also utilized to learn a foreign language. Interactivity refers to the student's interaction with a computer program or other cyberspace participants. These technologies take numerous forms:

- 1) The practice of communicating in a foreign language with students over the Internet in order to coordinate their independent work in between classroom classes, that is, the creation of cyber cabinet, for example, for instructing students, mailing

materials for them to view and complete assignments, as well as checking student's home and creative work with markings and marking errors using the (NOTES) function and sending back to the student by e-mail.

2) Test assignment activities for self-examination of assimilation of a given language topic.

3) Multimedia programs and training courses include interactive tasks (see and listen, read and repeat in pause), prompts, control, links to prior learning material, and progress tracking.

4) Mobile learning technologies use special gadgets (smartphones, netbooks, and etc.) to offer remote interactive training, which is in high demand in the tourist and hospitality industries today. As a result, special mobile software apps provide phone versions of grammars that include the right variant's pronunciation.

The Wordless feature enables you to send text or video contents, as well as assignments, from teacher's gadgets to students. Because the student's navigation protocol is saved in the LMS (learning management system), the teacher may keep track of whether the student visited the relevant page, how much time was spent there, and the outcome of this work. During remote learning, interactive materials enable the teacher to monitor assignment progress: completed assignments are marked with one color (for example, green), and outstanding ones with another (for example, red).

Electronic textbooks in a foreign language may contain all the necessary material, including interactive tasks in real time with elements of automated control or control by the teacher, and in delayed time mode with keys. Internet resources are a wonderful source for improving their thematic vocabulary by computer using the required parameters from any external material. This application enables students to transform from passive recipients of selected vocabulary teachers to active co-authors of their own professional and theme lexicon, continually refilling it. Internet tasks requiring significant reading of a variety of materials in preparation for an oral presentation. Web quests are an efficient way to teach undergraduate students to produce creative projects.

An interactive whiteboard combined with multimedia products allows students to not only demonstrate presentations, but also actively work with information in a variety of ways, such as correcting and underlining text, connecting the scheme with arrows, displaying the desired object on the screen using a hyperlink, animating text and photo materials, and so on.

METHODICAL FORMS

Role-playing games and simulations have grown commonplace. To effectively conduct such games in a tourist university, serious preparation is required. This includes determining grammatical structures and lexical units, as well as explaining optimal speech tactics to students unfamiliar with the industry and special disciplines. For example, when booking a tour, the manager must be aware of client's budget, preferences, and travel time, as well as propose several suitable options, explain what the tour price includes, inform the client of the rules and deadlines for paperwork, and the peculiarities of behavior in the country of travel, among other things. This knowledge can be provided to the learner via a teacher or a teacher recommended educational source. Business games can only be played with predetermined and exemplary scenario, which specifies the professional circumstances and problems. The game mood reflects the essence of speech interaction and aids in the resolution of management and creative problems during the communication process.

Consider design technology in the form of student-led projects in a foreign language. Creating a group project requires students to look for an objectively existing problem, develop their own tasks to solve it within the project, collaborate to find information and solutions, listen and hear each other during discussions, argue and persuade, object and make critical comments. In other words, learning a foreign language can help you acquire cooperative qualities like overcoming individualism and a lack of intermediate subject knowledge. However, it appears that the present concept of interaction in learning is not restricted to the aforementioned interpretations, such as the principle of learning or the associated types of learning. In the context of a specialized university, interactivity means something more: multifaceted interaction in

extracurricular time with a professional foreign language environment, which serves as a source of assailable experience in order to solve both professional and communicative arguments. According to specialists, a high degree of communicative abilities is still not an indicator of professional ability.

In contrast to professional development or advanced training for working professionals (in career training), students who lack professional experience and business expertise must be taught a foreign language alongside basic training, business principles and characteristics of tourism and hospitality industry. The scientific literature has already acknowledged the necessity for unity and interpenetration of trainees' educational and professional activities in teaching a foreign language for professional reasons.

Foreigners of first year students are educated from the very first weeks about the backdrop of "immersion" in the profession, which follows the student from the first to the last year and presents itself in various forms and activities. Let's name a few of them:

- 1) Attend or work on specialist tourism events.
- 2) Meetings with domestic travel industry specialists, who explain practical aspects of their sphere, followed by audience debate in foreign language.
- 3) Invited native speakers will deliver lectures on professional issues, followed by informal question and answer tasks with students and final classroom discussion with their teacher. Such gatherings are a vital aspect of the learning professional environment; they stimulate students' and the profession's enthusiasm in learning.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, there have been few statistically significant variations between students from different years of study in terms of the importance of the most essential foreign language in hospitality. There were no significant differences in the importance of the most important foreign language, specific types of tourism, or knowledge of

different languages among students from different years of study. There were no statistically significant differences in the importance of foreign language knowledge for elite and mass tourism among students from different years of study, but there was one statistically significant difference in the importance of knowing certain foreign languages for different services, while fourth year ACMT students in German is more difficult to learn than third year students do. As a result, we can partially confirm our initial theory. A key finding of our research into the differences between students from different years of study in terms of importance of knowing certain foreign languages is that, when compared to younger students consistently place a higher value on foreign language knowledge. This conclusion cannot be drawn because we discovered no statistically significant differences in the majority of the variables. This survey found that there is a need to continue promoting the learning of various foreign languages at a young age in order to establish efficient communication that allows for opinion exchanges and raise awareness about the importance of multilingual education for various areas of human activity, including tourism and business. In this regard, it is worth nothing that one of the most crucial abilities in tomorrow's Europe will be the capacity to communicate in multiple languages. Encouraging people to learn new languages and explore different cultures will help them communicate and understand each other better. It is also widely acknowledged that being able to converse directly in a foreign language can provide cultural and economic benefits to all parties in the communication process.

As a result, it is critical to raise awareness of the relevance of foreign language skills while also encouraging the development of intercultural competency in the tourism and hospitality industries.

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